

LIFE AND CREATIVE HERITAGE OF MUSA TASHMUHAMMAD OGLI OYBEK

Kodiriy Firdavsxon Nodirjon kizi

Student of Tashkent Textile and Light Industry Institute

fkodiriy1822@mail.ru

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7858659>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th April 2023

Accepted: 23th April 2023

Online: 24th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Uzbek literature, poetry, epic, novel, lyric, dramaturgy, translations.

ABSTRACT

The article provides information about the life and work of the famous Uzbek writer, poet and writer Musa Tashmuhammad oqli Oybek. Scientific opinions about the creative heritage of the writer are presented.

INTRODUCTION

The great representative of Uzbek literature, Musa Tashmuhammad oqli Oybek, is a poet, writer, translator, literary scholar and public figure. He created under the pseudonym Oybek. Oybek made a great contribution to the cultural development of the Uzbek people with his colorful creativity and his work as a great public figure. Literary skill has become a creative drug for young writers. Oybek's immortal works have forever taken a place in our spiritual treasure and have become public property. His best works are included in the treasury of world literature.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Musa Tashmuhammad oqli Oybek was born on January 10, 1905 in the city of Tashkent, in the Govkush neighborhood near Khadra square, in a family of a bozchi. His father, Tashmuhammad was a bozchi, and his mother, Shahodatbanu was educated, wise, honest and kind. Oybek later wrote about his childhood years in his book "Childhood" (1962), for which he was awarded the State Prize of the Uzbek SSR named after Hamza.

At first, in 1911-1917, Oybek received his primary education in the old school in Okmasjid neighborhood, and then in 1918-1921, in the "Namuna" school founded by Munavvargari Abdurashidkhanov. After that, in 1921-1925, after studying at the technical boarding school named after Navoi, in 1925-1927, he studied at the Faculty of Social Sciences of Tashkent University, and in 1927-1929, he studied at the Leningrad Institute of National Economy. After falling ill, he returned to Tashkent and graduated from Tashkent University in 1930.

Oybek's work began in his student years. In 1925-1927, he taught language and literature at secondary schools, technical schools, and labor faculties, at the National Economy, Agriculture, and Pedagogical Institutes, and in 1930-1935, he served as an assistant at the Faculty of Economics of Tashkent University. In 1933, he worked as a researcher at the

Scientific Research Institute of Cultural Construction and in 1934-1937 at the Institute of Language and Literature under the Committee of Sciences. In 1937, the escalation of the repression policy of the Soviet state caused Oybek to be fired from his job as a sympathizer of "nationalists" and "nationalists" - only at the end of the year, he was hired as a translator-editor at the Educational and Pedagogical Publishing House of Uzbekistan. In 1941-1945, with the beginning of the war, he was again persecuted as an unqualified person. In 1935-1951, the establishment of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan and after the death of Hamid Olimjon, he was appointed the chairman of the board of the Writers' Union, the editor-in-chief of the "Eastern Star" magazine in 1945-1959, the director of the Institute of Language and Literature in 1950-1952, and In 1951, he served as the editor-in-chief of the magazine "Uzbek language and literature". In the early 1950s, as another wave of repression began, Oybek suffered a stroke on April 16, 1951, and died on July 1, 1968 at the age of 63 after a long illness. The writer was buried in the Chigatai cemetery.

Oybek's active civic role and bright creativity can be seen from his achievements. In 1943, the writer was an academician of the FA of Uzbekistan SSR, a deputy of the 5th and 6th convocations of the General Council of the SSR, a member of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union since 1948, and in 1965 he was awarded the title of People's Writer of Uzbekistan and plab was awarded with orders and medals of the USSR, in particular with the Order of Lenin. He was also a laureate of the Republican State Prize named after Hamza.

After Oybek's death, a collection of his works in 20 volumes was published, and in 2001, the poet was awarded the Order of Merit. In 1980, the house-museum of Oybek was established in the house where the writer lived, and a statue was installed in it. A school, an avenue and one of the metro stations in Tashkent are named after Oybek, Termiz State University, collective farm in Tashkent region is named after Oybek.

Musa Tashmuhammad ogli Oybek

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Oybek's literary career began as a poet, and his first poem called "The Sound of an Instrument" was published in Armugon magazine in 1922. Although his main creative years

correspond to the 1930s and 1960s, his first collection of poems entitled "Feelings" was written in 1926. Then, in 1929, a collection called "Kongil naylari" was published.

In his early work, Oybek created poems devoted to the passing themes of the time, and most of them were published in the collection "Mashala" (1932). Later, the poet paid great attention to the depiction of lyrical feelings and experiences, and wrote "Chimyon's Notebook". He created poems that express the charming freshness and unique colors of Uzbek nature, belonging to the series. These poems became one of the royal examples not only of the poet's poetic creativity, but also of Uzbek lyrics in general. With these poems, the poet brought the unique and elegant lyricism to Uzbek poetry, perfected the culture of describing delicate feelings and experiences, and polished the language of lyric poetry with the rain of elegance.

As a result of the literary and cultural policy of the Soviet state in 1937-1938, the principle of approaching writers and their works from the point of view of vulgar sociology became stronger. Oybek's lyrical poems included in the series "Chimyon's Notebook" were evaluated as examples of bourgeois poetry. As a result of this movement, which rose to the level of state policy, along with other poets, Oybek was forced to create examples of poetry called "Fajdan poetry". Nevertheless, Oybek's works such as "Uzbekistan", "Dneprostroy", "Walk to science", "Raisa", "Girls", which encourage the acquisition of science and technology and are imbued with the ideas of patriotism and hard work. Many poems and epics were an important event in Uzbek poetry in the 1930s and 1940s.

Along with lyrical poetry, Oybek also researched in the field of epic writing. "Gulnoz", "Kamonchi", in 1937 he wrote epics such as "Navoiy". In these epics, the poet created the image of the hero of his time and raised the important social and spiritual issues of this period, and also addressed the topic of the historical past.

In the late 1940s and early 1950s, in addition to the epic "Girls" (1947), Oybek created the epics "Hamza" (1948), "Zafar va Zahro" (1950) and "Veracious" (1952). Along with writing epics about the tragedy of the city of Hiroshima, "The wound of my time" (1952), "Guli and Navoi" (1968), he began to write lyrical epics about Amir Timur and Babur. With these works, the poet made an important contribution to the beginning and settlement of a new artistic thinking in the Uzbek poetry of the 60s.

Oybek's first experience in the novel genre - "Blessed blood" was written in the most dangerous period of the writer's life, in 1938, and published in 1940. This work, saturated with the writer's childhood memories, describes the hardships of the Uzbek people on the eve of the First World War. written about his life.

During this period, due to the colonial policy, on the one hand, and capitalist relations, which began to enter the country, on the other hand, the masses of workers were extremely impoverished. At such a time, it was natural for the impatient people to protest or raise an uprising. The decree of the tsarist authorities on the recruitment of the people of Central Asia into labor became an impetus for the roaring and burning of the 1916 uprising. Oybek artistically analyzed the causes of this uprising by describing the mutual relations between Yolchi headman, workers, Mirzakarimboy headman and rich people in the novel.

With this work, Oybek developed the tradition of historical novelists started by Abdulla Kadiri, Cholpon and Sadridin Ainiy, and enriched it with bright images of heroes such as

Yolchi and Gulnor, who embodied the character of the hardworking people. "Blessed Blood" is one of the most artistic novels in Uzbek literature.

Although Oybek's novel "The Sun does not darken", written in 1943-1959, dedicated to the bravery of the Uzbek people in the Second World War, began to be written after his trip to the Western Front, it was impossible to tell the terrible truth about the war. because of this, he finished writing this work during his illness in the 50s. By creating the image of Bektemir and his two comrades-in-arms, Oybek artistically revealed the fact that the Soviet state entered the war unprepared and due to the gross mistakes of the generals, millions of people, including Uzbek fighters, were the target of bullets. In the novel "Breezes from the Golden Valley" written in 1949, Adib tried to embody the image of the hero of the post-war period, and in the work "Great way" written in 1967 as a continuation of the novel "Blessed blood" the image of Yolchi and Gulnor's followers in the 1920.

As a literary scholar, Oybek often referred to the life of Navoi. His novel "Navoi" written in 1942 at the height of the Second World War skillfully embodied not only the great poet, but also the humanity of Navoi as a poet and human being. Oybek embodied the image of Navoi against the background of the important historical events that took place in Khurasan of the 15th century, and reflected the forces that brought the Timurid state into action during this period, and later brought it to decline, and their mutual struggle. With this work, Oybek started the historical-biographical novel genre in Uzbek literature and defined its main principles. The novel "Navoi" later inspired the creation of historical and biographical novels in Uzbek literature such as "Treasure of Ulugbek", "Old World" (Odil Yakubov), "Starry Nights", "Generations' Nek" (Pirimkul Kadirov).

An important part of Oybek's literary activity is research and articles on literary studies. He published many articles devoted to the formation and development of Uzbek literature from the earliest period to the 60s of the last century. A large part of these articles was dedicated to the study of Alisher Navoi's life, poet's life and work, and they later formed the collection of articles "Navoi's Gulshan" by Oybek. These articles contributed to the formation and development of Navoi studies as an important field in Uzbek literature. At the same time, together with A. Deych, Oybek published a series of articles on Navoi in Russian.

In his monograph "Abdulla Kadiri's creative path" (1935) and other articles, the great literary critic Oybek scientifically analyzed the problems of the development of Uzbek literature in the 20th century and Russian literary figures who influenced Uzbek writers, such as Alexander Pushkin, Lev Tolstoy and Maxim Gorky learned.

Oybek, a master of creativity, translated the highest examples of world and Russian literature into Uzbek language and enriched the Uzbek translation school founded by Cholpon and Abdulla Qadiri with his high-level translations. Samples of Roman literature translated by Uzbek book reader Oybek, "Tartuf" by J.B. Molyem, "Eugene Onegin" by Alexander Pushkin, "Masquerade" by Mikhail Lermontov, Armenian epic "Davud Sosunli", G. Geyne, I.A. Krylov, V.G. Belinsky, E. Verharn and got acquainted with the works of others.

CONCLUSION:

In the centuries-old history of Uzbek literature, the literature of the 20th century occupies a special place. In this century, Uzbek literature absorbed the best artistic achievements of Eastern and Western literature and was enriched with great works created in

all types and genres of artistic creativity. The merits of Musa Tashmuhammad ogli Oybek in conquering the great creative passes of Uzbek literature in the 20th century are especially great. He continued the best literary traditions of his teachers, Abdulla Kadiri and Cholpon, and brought Uzbek literature and literary studies to a new stage of development with his immortal prose and poetic works, scientific and literary-critical articles.

Oybek enriched the treasury of Uzbek literature with his novels and short stories, scientific-theoretical, political, artistic journalistic works, translations, wonderful poems, epics, stories. Oybek's poems, stories, short stories and epics effectively influence human spirituality and play a major role in the formation of the aesthetic taste of the young generation. In particular, Oybek's poetic works reflect today's hot life, love for science, craft and work, patriotism, public awareness, and social duty.

References:

1. Koshjanov M. Oybek skills. -T.: Literary Publishing House, 1965
2. Karimov N. Oybek. Scenes from the life and work of the famous Uzbek writer.Tashkent: Young Guard, 1985.
3. Karimov N. Buds left in Oybek's gulshan. - Tashkent, 1985.
4. Oybek. A perfect collection of works. (19 volumes) - T.: Science, 1975-1982.
5. History of contemporary Uzbek literature. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1931
6. Sabriddinov A. Oybek's poetic skill. - T.: Science, 2006.
7. Oybek. Navoi. Roman. T.: Teacher, 1985